

Immersion Pyknometer.

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The hydrostatic method of estimating the specific gravity of solids offers no difficulty so long as the estimation of a large piece of solid is concerned but is not convenient for coarse grains and fine powders usually met with in technical practice. In the following is described a form of the pyknometer called the immersion pyknometer which allows the density determinations, especially of powders to be made accurately and easily.

The immersion pyknometer (see Figure) is made of glass or quartz.

It contains an empty vessel (D) of about 1 to 10 c.c. capacity, in which a capillary tube (C) is well ground in. This capillary tube and the vessel carry glass (or quartz) hooks (B) from which are hung two $V_2 A$ springs. The ground joint is not, therefore, greased and allows the apparatus to be used with organic substances. The capillary also carries a glass or quartz hoop (A) to which a thin platinum wire could be stuck. While weighing under immersion, the instrument is hung with the help of the wire so that always a constant length of it is under the liquid.

Before use, the apparatus is washed with pure alcohol and ether and dried in vacuum.

The powder whose density is to be determined is weighed out in the pyknometer itself in air and then in water. The substance is covered with air-free distilled water. The pyknometer vessel is placed in a vacuum desiccator and all the air is sucked out. Then, through a connection to a flask of the air-free distilled water, the desiccator is gradually filled with water till the pyknometer is also filled. The pyknometer is taken out, wiped dry and weighed under water at a constant temperature. Then

$$s = \frac{(p_2 - p_1)}{(p_2 - p_1) - (p_3 - p_4)}$$

where s denotes the density of powder, p_1 , the wt. of empty pyknometer, p_2 , wt. of pyknometer with substance, p_3 , wt. under water of the pyknometer with substance and p_4 , the wt. under water of empty pyknometer.

The following table shows the accuracy of the instruments into four different powders. These powders are those usually met with in ceramic works.

TABLE I.

Temperature = 16°.

(a)	$s = 2.509$	(b)	$s = 2.494$	(c)	$s = 3.837$	(d)	$s = 2.865$
	2.509		2.494		3.837		2.865
	2.509		2.493		3.837		2.865
	2.509		2.494		3.838		2.865

The immersion pyknometer can also be used with any liquid other than water, whose specific gravity is known, and which does not necessarily dissolve the solid.

In this case, p_3 and p_4 would represent the weights under the liquid of density σ instead of water. Then the density of solid

$$s = \frac{(p_2 - p_1)\sigma}{(p_2 - p_1) - (p_3 - p_4)}$$

Immersion pyknometer can also be used for the determination of the density of liquids in a very elegant way. The pyknometer is used as an immersion body as in the case of Mohr-Westphal balance. The density of liquid is given by

$$\sigma = \frac{p_1 - p_2}{p_1 - p_3}$$

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